

ROZWÓJ OGÓLNOTEORETYCZNYCH PODSTAW KRYMINALISTYKI NA UKRAINIE

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Adnotacja. W artykule przedstawiono rozwój ogólnoteoretycznych podstaw kryminalistyki na Ukrainie oraz ich znaczenie dla praktyki prawoznawczej. W strukturze podstaw ogólnoteoretycznych wyodrębniono prognozowanie kryminalistyczne oraz strategię kryminalistyczną. Zaprezentowano rolę różnych organizacji kryminalistycznych w udoskonalaniu rozwoju ogólnoteoretycznych podstaw kryminalistyki na Ukrainie, spośród których zaakcentowano działalność Międzynarodowego Kongresu Kryminalistów (INGO «Criminalists Congress»). Wyznaczono strategiczne kierunki działalności organów ścigania w przeciwdziałaniu przestępczości zorganizowanej na Ukrainie. Określono przepisy dotyczące prognozowania kryminalistycznego oraz strategii kryminalistycznej, które są zawarte w dokumentach normatywnych zabezpieczających działalność poszczególnych organów ścigania Ukrainy - Ministerstwa Spraw Wewnętrznych oraz Służby Eksperckiej. Wyciągnięto wnioski, iż rozwój ogólnoteoretycznych podstaw kryminalistyki na Ukrainie jest podstawą do opracowania strategicznych kierunków przeciwdziałania przestępczości. Znaczącymi wyznacznikami tego procesu są zmiany w zakresie ustawodawstwa karnego oraz karnego procesowego, osiągnięcia i perspektywy progresu naukowo-technicznego, trendy stanowienia kryminalistyki światowej. Położono nacisk na współczesnej konieczności opracowania programu międzyresortowego dotyczącego przeciwdziałaniu przestępczości na Ukrainie.

Słowa kluczowe: ogólnoteoretyczne podstawy kryminalistyki, prognozowanie kryminalistyczne, strategia kryminalistyczna, rozwój Ministerstwa Spraw Wewnętrznych Ukrainy, rozwój Służby Eksperckiej MSW Ukrainy.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE GENERAL FORENSIC THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES IN UKRAINE

Abstract. The article reveals the development of the general forensic theoretical principles in Ukraine, their significance for law enforcement practice. Forensic forecasting and forensic strategy are distinguished in the structure of general theoretical foundations. The role of various forensic organizations in the improvement of the development of the general theoretical foundations of the forensics in Ukraine (especially activities of the International Criminalists Congress (INGO «Criminalists Congress»)) are studied. The strategic directions of activity of law enforcement bodies in counteraction to organized criminal activity in Ukraine are defined. The provisions of forensic forecasting and forensic strategy, which are contained in the normative documents, providing activity of separate law enforcement bodies of Ukraine – the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the Expert Service, are covered. It is concluded that the development of the general theoretical foundations of the forensics in Ukraine is the basis for developing strategic directions of combating crime. The determining factors of this process are changes in criminal and criminal procedural legislation, achievements and prospects of scientific and technological

progress, trends in the formation of the world forensics. The modern need to prepare an interdepartmental program on the strategy of combating crime in Ukraine is stated.

Keywords: general forensic theoretical principles, forensic forecasting, forensic strategy, development of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, development of the Expert Service of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine.

РОЗВИТОК ЗАГАЛЬНОТЕОРЕТИЧНИХ ОСНОВ КРИМІНАЛІСТИКИ В УКРАЇНІ

Анотація. У статті розкрито розвиток загальнотеоретичних основ криміналістики в Україні, їх значення для правозастосовної практики. У структурі загальнотеоретичних основ виокремлено криміналістичне прогнозування та криміналістичну стратегію. Розкрито роль різних криміналістичних організацій в удосконаленні розвитку загальнотеоретичних основ криміналістики в Україні, серед яких акцентовано на діяльності Міжнародного конгресу криміналістів (INGO «Criminalists Congress»). Визначено стратегічні напрями діяльності правоохоронних органів у протидії організованій злочинній діяльності в Україні. Висвітлено положення криміналістичного прогнозування та криміналістичної стратегії, що містяться у нормативних документах, забезпечуючих діяльність окремих правоохоронних органів України – Міністерства внутрішніх справ і Експертної служби. Зроблено висновки, що розвиток загальнотеоретичних основ криміналістики в Україні є основою для розроблення стратегічних напрямів протидії злочинності. Визначальними чинниками цього процесу є зміни кримінального та кримінального процесуального законодавства, досягнення і перспективи науково-технічного прогресу, тенденції становлення світової криміналістики. Констатовано сучасну необхідність підготовки міжвідомчої програми щодо стратегії протидії злочинності в Україні.

Ключові слова: загальнотеоретичні основи криміналістики, криміналістичне прогнозування, криміналістична стратегія, розвиток Міністерства внутрішніх справ України, розвиток Експертної служби МВС України.

Introduction. Theoretical foundations of the forensics form a system of basic principles, theoretical concepts, categories, terms and methods, which are the methodological basis for the development of this science.

Without knowledge of the general theoretical foundations of the forensics it is impossible to effectively ensure the practice of scientific and technical achievements, namely: to study the needs of law-enforcement practice in scientific recommendations; to develop recommendations on the technical-forensic, tactical-forensic, expert-forensic and methodological support of law-enforcement practice; to expand the sphere of application of the developed technical-forensic means in combating crime; to create the appropriate scientific and methodological support for the use of technical and forensic means; to intensify the introduction of technical and forensic means into practice; to check the effectiveness of the developed forensics tools, techniques, methods (*Piaskovskiy V., 2015, pp. 21–22*).

Questions of the general theory of the forensics in Ukraine were studied by V. P. Bahin, A. F. Volobuyev, V. G. Honcharenko, V. A. Zhuravel, A. V. Ishchenko, V. O. Konovalova, V. G. Lukashevich, G. A. Matusovskyi, V. V. Tishchenko, V. Yu. Shepitko and others. At the same time, aspects of the effectiveness of the general provisions of forensic science for the practice of investigating crimes and combating crime in general are poorly researched.

The purpose of the article is to reveal the general theoretical foundations of forensics in the aspect of perspective directions of its development in Ukraine and the significance for law enforcement practice.

Main material. Forensic science is a developing science, its boundaries are expanding, new directions and theories arise. Modern development of the forensics is characterized by the formation of general and individual theories, the development and implementation of the latest scientific and technical means and information technologies in the practice of counteraction to crime, the improvement of methods of forensic tactics, the offering of separate methods of investigation of new types of crimes.

The development of the general theoretical foundations of the forensics in Ukraine is connected with its tasks at the present stage, which are defined by the social function of this science. The general task of the forensics is to assist law enforcement and judicial authorities in combating crime, full and timely technical and forensic provision and support in the disclosure and investigation of crimes, their trial. One of the separate tasks of forensic science is the further development of separate theories of science (*Kuzmichov V., 2001, p. 8*), primarily general theoretical foundations.

The development of general theoretical foundations foresees the possibility of forensic forecasting. This also applies to the prevention of crime. Forensics must work to predict and prevent what may become crimes in the near future. This is associated with further development and improvement of the theory of the forensic prediction (*Bahin V., 2002, p. 15*).

The general theoretical foundations of the forensics in Ukraine should correspond to the relevant world forensic tendencies. One of the channels which determine such compliance, necessary adjustments are participation of the national forensic specialists in the scientific activities of various forensic organizations, institutions and scientific societies (European Network of Forensic Science Institutes (ENFSI), Fingerprint Society (FPS), International Association for Identification (IAI), Lithuanian Forensic Society, Polish Forensic Society, International Non-Governmental Organization «Criminalists Congress»), holding international scientific events (conferences, congresses, symposiums) (*Shepitko V., 2014, pp. 151–152*).

In particular, the International Congress of Criminalists is a public organization founded on the Constituent Conference in Kharkiv (Ukraine) on 17 February 2012. At the conference, the Statute of the Congress was adopted. Thus, the purpose of the community's activity is to unite efforts to promote the development of the forensics and other related fields of knowledge, as well as the promotion of forensic knowledge. The Congress implements its purpose through its tasks: to ensure the protection of human and citizen rights from unlawful encroachments; introduction of the most effective methods, methods and means of countering crime, the latest achievements of investigative and judicial practice, as well as forensic research; definition of the main directions of development of the forensics, its inter-scientific relations with criminal law and process, and other branches of knowledge; reports on the most significant criminalistics events, advanced investigation and judicial practice; establishing personal contacts through the direct exchange of scientific and professional experience between members of the Congress, conducting joint scientific events; coordination, assistance and promotion of the scientific, professional, educational and educational activities of the forensic specialists; promoting the exchange of publications between members of the Congress etc.

Effective realization of the tasks of forensic science within the framework of developing its general theoretical bases involves studying the regularities of criminal activity for the proper use of means and methods of detection, counteraction and neutralization of this socially negative phenomenon. In the forensic science of Ukraine, the question of determining the regularities of criminal activity to date remains badly investigated.

Taking into account the work of one of the authors of the research, the definition of the regularities of criminal activity and its structure were determined. Thus, in the structure of criminal activity, the purpose, object, subject, means, result, mechanism are determined. The regularities of criminal activity reproduce the interconnection and interdependence between its purpose, object, subject, means, result, mechanism, expressed in the environment in the form of material and ideal traces (*Yusupov V., 2018, p. 177, 221*). At the same time, there is a need for further more in-depth study of the elements of criminal activity, especially of its dangerous manifestations – professional, organized, transnational and others. For example, we consider strategic directions of activity of law enforcement agencies in counteracting organized crime in Ukraine:

Identification and documentation of the activities of criminal organizations, organized groups, primarily associated with activities in the shadow economy, and the disclosure of crimes committed by them;

Identification of corruption links in central and regional state bodies and the links of organized criminal structures in the legislative, executive and judicial authorities;

Execution of administrative powers concerning the manifestations of illegal behavior of members of criminal structures in accordance with the defined competence;

Further improvement of the organization of international cooperation in the field of combating organized crime.

The most potentially productive areas of counteraction to organized crime in the economy of Ukraine are analytical intelligence, the transition to enriched information-scientific and prognostic forms of activity of law enforcement units of economy security, the study of materials of covert surveillance, operational units, reports of silent workers, data interceptions from various communication channels, as well as analysis of reports, publications and performances in the mass media, statistics, summaries contained in different automatized databases and information systems.

The development of the general theoretical foundations of the forensics is substantially influenced by changes in the criminal and criminal procedural legislation, the achievement of scientific and technological progress, the tendencies of the formation of world forensics.

In Ukraine, nowadays, the number of bodies that carry out pre-trial investigation of the committed crimes has increased. In accordance with the Criminal Procedure Code of Ukraine, which has been in force since 1961, the investigation was conducted by investigators of only three units – the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Prosecutor's Office and the Security Service. With the current CPC, the number of such structures has increased to six. The emergence of new law enforcement agencies investigating perpetrated crimes is related to the specifics of these offenses. Thus, investigators of the State Fiscal Service are investigating a number of crimes related to violations of tax legislation, detectives of the National Anti-Corruption Bureau – crimes committed by senior state officials, or as causing losses in particularly large amounts etc.

It should be borne in mind that in Ukraine the authorities have the power to investigate the crimes committed, and therefore the most used are the provisions of

forensic science, which, besides the investigators of the National Police coordinated by the Ministry of Internal Affairs, are also subordinated to the relevant Departments of the Security Service, the State Fiscal Service, the State Bureau of Investigations (at the stage of creation), The National Anti-Corruption Bureau of Ukraine, the State Penitentiary Service. In connection with this, it is necessary to develop an anti-crime strategy in Ukraine, which would include inter-departmental directions of the relevant activity.

In our country the basics of forensic strategy were developed by V. D. Bernaz, V. A. Zhuravel, V. Yu. Shepitko and others.

In particular, V. D. Bernas believes that the content of the crime investigation strategy should cover: the definition of priorities and the judicial prospect of the investigation; development and implementation of directions in achieving the objectives of the investigation; modeling and realization of reflexive management of crime investigation in general; forecasting in a criminal case; development of algorithm for typical strategic operations; organization and management of the investigation of both separate criminal cases and all cases that are in the conduct of the investigator; organization and management of the investigation of cases, which are carried out by the brigade of investigative or investigative-task forces; adoption of key procedural decisions in a criminal case; formation in the population's readiness to participate in the disclosure and investigation of crimes (*Bernas V., 2010, p. 208*).

Strategic for forensics can be considered a task of forecasting its development. The forensic strategy is related to the criminal policy of the state and society, the development of the science of the forensics in the world, the separate areas of forensic forecasting, the development of modern scientific and technical means, information technologies and their implementation in the practice of counteracting crime (*Shepitko V., 2014, p. 151*).

In Ukraine, the basics of forensic strategy are partly reflected in certain documents. Namely – the Strategy development of the MIA of Ukraine till 2020, Strategy Development of the Expert Service of the MIA of Ukraine for the period till 2020. Lets briefly analyze these important documents.

One of the goals of the Strategy Development of the MIA (MIA Strategy 2017) is to create a safe environment for the development of a free society and ensure high efficiency of the activities of the bodies of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. This, of course, provides for the organization of work units for the rapid and complete disclosure of crimes, the application of effective prevention measures in the state.

The importance of the optimal decision-making process, which should take into account the positive experience and best practices of the leading powers, as well as successful international crime-fighting practices, are very important.

In this aspect, such priority measures of international cooperation may be considered:

Implementation of measures to increase the effectiveness of the activities of the National Central Bureau of Interpol in Ukraine;

Comprehensive introduction of modern criminal analysis systems, including the Europol methodology;

Activization of information cooperation, quick and efficient exchange (if motivated the need for simplified procedure approval) with forensic and operational records and other information of operational nature;

Studying and implementing international experience in the field of criminalistics, first of all, by integrating the expert service into the system of forensic institutions of Europe;

Expansion of overseas internships, trainings and other types of training and exchange of experience, primarily grass-roots workers and middle managers who directly ensure the rights and duties of citizens engaged in the prevention and fight against crime, ensuring public safety;

Intensification of international cooperation in the field of training for the units of the National Police and in the field of research.

Implementation of the Development Strategy of the MIA provides for the provision of an adequate level of technical and material equipment of pre-trial investigation bodies and the use of modern expert-forensic means in their activities; Development of the juvenile prevention system; Preparation in cooperation with other authorized bodies of preventive programs and programs for ensuring citizens safety; Development of the system for preventing emergencies and preventing criminal explosions and fires.

At present, increased forensic provision are needed by the investigative units that are territorially deployed in settlements in the territory of which the state authorities temporarily do not exercise their powers, as well as temporarily occupied territory of Ukraine.

An important approach in the work of the relevant bodies of the Ministry of Internal Affairs is the involvement of society in the process of creating a safe environment, which is along with the fight against crime as a priority area of activity.

Interaction between different law enforcement agencies needs to be improved. In this aspect, the Development Strategy of the MIA provides development of interaction between the State Migration Service of Ukraine, the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine and the National Police of Ukraine on the issues of counteraction to transborder crime, human trafficking etc. This will increase crime countering in the border areas of the state.

The Development Strategy of the MIA has an emphasis on strengthening the fight against organized crime, combating human trafficking and illegal migration, drug crime and cybercrime; illicit trafficking and the use of weapons and explosive substances; development of international cooperation in the field of combating transnational crime. In addition, provision of full security of society is impossible without forensic provision of the national security sector.

Thus, the Development Strategy of the MIA of Ukraine provides most current ways of forensic activity in the authorities that belong to its sphere of government – the National Police (most - investigative units of the National Police), State Emergency Service, Administration of the State Border Guard Service, the State Migration Service, and the National Guard.

Development Strategy of the Expert Service of the MIA of Ukraine (Expert Service Strategy 2017) envisages improvement of forensic expert activity in the areas of forensic examination in criminal, administrative, civil and commercial affairs, as well as research in extrajudicial proceedings on the basis of operational and investigative activities. One of the ways to achieve this goal is to improve judicial and expert activities/technical and forensic provision of operational units, bodies of pre-trial investigation and the court for the prevention, detection, disclosure and investigation of criminal and other offenses.

In this way, it is necessary to carry out new areas of expert research: amphibious embryonic research; research of destroyed parts and mechanisms; telecommunication studies; integration into international databases of forensic and investigative information.

An important aspect of the development of the Expert Service of the Ministry of Internal Affairs is the further deepening of international cooperation. Nowadays, this is the interaction between expert institutions of Ukraine and the European network of forensic institutions. Membership in ENFSI involves two types of memberships: the membership of forensic institutions of countries belonging to the European Union, and the membership of forensic institutions of countries not belonging to it. The ENFSI member may be an institution or forensic institution that must hold at least half of the types of expertise in its country and has a state status. At least 25 people must work in the such expert institution (*Khaziev Sh., 2005, p. 15*). Currently working groups have been created in the structure of the ENFSI: digital images in forensic examination; genetic identification; forensic study of documents; study of narcotic drugs; research of fibers; study of traces of hands; firearms research; computer-technical expertise; forensic examination of speech, voice and sounds; handwriting study; forensic trasological research; forensic examination of varnishes and paints; forensic examination of road traffic events; study of the crime scene; study of fires and explosions (*Tomin S., 2010, p. 749*). ENFSI includes 63 leading expert and forensic institutions from 36 European countries. Since March 2002, the Main Department of the Expert Service – the State Research Experimental Forensic Center of the MIA of Ukraine has been accredited as the laboratory in accordance with the requirements of the international standard ISO/IEC 17025. The standard general requirements of the ISO/IEC 17025 to the competence of test and calibration laboratories are the main standard, which applies to forensic institutions in order to guarantee the implementation of control and compliance with quality requirements. It is one of the components of ensuring the implementation of the minimum standards of forensic expertise of national practice (*Simakova-Yefremian E., 2016, p. 13*). The use of molecular genetic research in Ukraine in international judicial co-operation cooperation is especially popular.

The prospect of this area of cooperation will be to further unify, certify and standardize both the methods of expertise and laboratory equipment.

For realization of the Development Strategy of the Expert Service of the MIA of Ukraine it is envisaged:

Deployment of full-fledged forensic laboratories with appropriate logistics, further their accreditation at the level of international standards;

Development, gradual automation and connection of systems of expert forensic accounting services to the integrated informational search system of the National Police of Ukraine;

DNA-technologies development;

Further improvement of forensic accounting.

Relevant in this area is the replenishment of forensic records with such new types as fixation of the iris of the retina, video recognition of a person by image, X-ray of the body, genomic portraits (*Sokurenko V., 2017, p. 26*).

Modern development of the forensics is characterized by the development and implementation of the latest scientific and technical means and information technologies in the practice of counteraction to crime, improvement of methods of forensic tactics, the offering of separate methods of investigation of new types of crimes. The development and formation of forensic knowledge is conditioned by the scientific and technological progress of modern society. Informatization of the social environment has led to «technologicalization» of the forensics, the development and implementation of

information, digital, telecommunication and other technologies. In the new conditions, the forensics from the study of traditional material-fixed traces should go to the study of sound, electronic or genomic traces. The methods of working with such traces, the order of their collection, research and fixation are also changing (Shepitko Yu., 2017, pp. 7–8).

The forensics modernizes the adaptation of the modern equipment for the technical and forensic support of investigative (search) actions (in particular, the use of the global satellite positioning systems (GPS devices, etc), laser 3D-scanners during inspection of the crime scene) (Yusupov V., 2018, p. 482).

Conclusions. Consequently, the development of the general theoretical foundations of the forensics in Ukraine is the basis for developing strategic directions for combating crime. Important factors affecting them are changes in criminal and criminal procedural legislation, achievements and prospects of scientific and technological progress, trends in the formation of world forensics.

At the present stage, preparation of an interdepartmental program on the strategy of combating crime in Ukraine is extremely necessary. And the development of an appropriate strategy to combat crime on the basis of the general theoretical foundations of the forensics will ensure the achievement of a positive strategic outcome.

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